

On Colloidal Ampholytes : The Effect of Neutral Salts on Isoionic Bovine Serum Albumin and the Dissociation Constant of its Carboxyl Groups between pH 2.0 and 5.0

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The observation of Scatchard, Coleman and Shen that the pH of isoionic bovine serum mercapt-albumin (BSA) solution rises with increasing concentration of an added neutral salt has been explained on the basis of author's theory without assuming anion binding by BSA.

The binding of H⁺ ions by BSA has been accounted for quantitatively by an equation derived from author's theory on "Colloidal Electrolytes" discussed in previous papers. The dissociation constant of the COOH groups in BSA between pH 2.0 and 5.0 has been found to be 10^{-3.18} (i.e., pK = 3.18).

IN several previous publications¹⁻⁷ it has been shown that variation, with dilution, of such properties of colloidal electrolytes as osmotic pressure, specific conductivity and counter ion activity can be accounted for by equations deduced from a theory proposed by the author.

It has been shown^{1,2} that the variation of H⁺ ion activity of a solution of a colloidal acid can be represented by the following equation :

$$(H) = \theta H_s + (1 - \theta) H_i \quad \dots (1)$$

In equation (1) (H) and H_i represent the activity of the H⁺ ions in the colloidal solution and the intermicellar liquid respectively, H_s is a proportionality constant and may be interpreted to represent the H⁺ ion activity associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the reversible electrode, θ , the fraction per unit area of the electrode surface in contact with the diffuse double layers of the particles. θ has been found to be equal to $C/(K+C)$, where C is the concentration (Unit arbitrary) of the colloidal particles and K a constant.

For a well-dialysed colloidal acid sol when θ is fairly large the following equation has been deduced in previous papers^{6,7}.

$$p(H) = p(\theta K_s) + n \log(\alpha)/(1 - \alpha) \quad \dots (2)$$

where (H) and θ have the same significance as stated already, K_s has been termed the surface dissociation constant and α the degree of dissociation (i.e., the bare fraction of the acidic groups per unit area of the Stern-Mukherjee layer) and n is a number not less than unity.

Scatchard, Coleman and Shen¹⁰ have observed that when neutral salts like NaCl are added to isoionic bovine serum mercapt-albumin (BSA) the pH of the solution, measured by the glass-electrode, increases with the increasing concentration of the added salt. To account for this observation they have assumed that there are groups of sites on the surface of the spherical BSA macromolecule which can bind anions, each group having its characteristic affinity. On the basis of this theory of anion binding and increased electrostatic attraction they have derived an equation which has been found to agree fairly with their data on salt concentration and rise of pH of isoionic BSA. The aforesaid authors have also investigated the binding of H⁺ ions and anions by BSA from its mixtures with acids, but the binding of ions from the said solutions could not be accounted for on the basis of their theory.

In this paper it will be shown how far the theory proposed by the author can account for the results obtained by Scatchard, Coleman and Shen¹⁰. It may be mentioned that according to Nagasawa and Holtzer¹¹ the rise of pH produced by the action of neutral salts on isoionic BSA may be due to specific conformation of discrete charges rather than by ion binding.

Experimental results of Scatchard, Coleman and Shen with explanatory notes :

Scatchard, Coleman and Shen¹⁰ have investigated the binding of H⁺ and Cl⁻ ions by BSA from its mixtures with acids using glass electrode for measuring (H) the H⁺ ion activity and resin membrane electrode for measuring Cl⁻ ion activity. In Table 1 are recorded the values of m_1 , m_2 , pH and ν_x taken from Table 2 of their paper¹⁰. m_1

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF THE COOH GROUPS IN BSA BETWEEN pH 2.0 AND 5.0

$m_1 \times 10^5$	$m_2 \times 10^4$	pH	$H_c \times 10^4$	ν_x	$(X^-) \times 10^4$	$(Cl_c) \times 10^4$	$(Cl_i) \times 10^4$ or $(H_i) \times 10^4$	$(HCl_i) \times 10^4$	(H_b)	$n \log \alpha / (1-\alpha)$	pK_s
7.691	1.936	4.83	0.148	0.28	1.721	1.680	0.498	0.50	1.86	1.64	3.19
8.375	7.310	4.40	0.398	1.59	5.983	5.821	1.523	1.55	6.80	1.03	3.37
8.017	18.620	3.73	1.862	4.18	15.270	14.640	5.233	5.37	16.60	0.58	3.15
12.420	34.430	3.59	2.570	6.07	26.880	25.550	8.090	8.34	21.10	0.43	3.16
8.072	67.300	2.90	12.590	13.30	56.580	52.440	25.690	27.05	49.80	-0.26	3.16
12.420	102.500	2.84	14.450	18.10	79.700	72.930	32.460	34.60	54.50	-0.38	3.22
11.780	197.700	2.12	75.860	34.60	156.900	140.200	103.000	114.40	70.70	-1.07	3.19

and m_2 represent respectively the stoichiometric concentration of BSA and HCl taken initially, ν_x represents the number of Cl^- ions bound by one mole (molecular weight 69,000) of BSA. They¹⁰ have actually measured X^- but recorded ν_x instead of it, ν_x being calculated from X^- using the equation, $\nu_x = (m_2 - X^-)/m_1$. We have recalculated X^- using their data and the aforesaid equation. Each value of X^- represents that concentration of HCl (without BSA) which has got the same Cl^- ion activity as the corresponding mixture of HCl and BSA. Each value of Cl_c in Table 1 (representing the Cl^- ion activity of the corresponding mixture of BSA and HCl) has been calculated from the corresponding value of X^- using Young and Randall's¹² data on activity coefficient of HCl supplemented by Hitchcock¹³ equation where necessary. Each value of H_i or Cl_i (representing the activity of the H^+ or Cl^- ions in the intermicellar solution) has been found by applying Donnan's theory of membrane equilibrium in the way indicated by the author in a previous paper⁴ [i.e. $H_i = Cl_i = \sqrt{(HC)(Cl_c)}$]. HCl_i represents the concentration of HCl in the intermicellar solution and each of its value has been found from the corresponding value of Cl_i using the proper activity coefficient. H_b represents the H^+ ions (gram ions) bound by one mole of BSA and has been found from the expression $H_b = (m_2 - HCl_i)/m_1$. Assuming Y , to be equal to the number of COOH groups present in a mole of BSA, α in equation (2) is found from the expression $\alpha = (Y - H_b)/Y$. It has been found by trial that $Y = 77$ and $n = 1.02$.

Discussion

Many authors¹⁴⁻¹⁷ have observed that lyophobic colloids become resistant to coagulation by electrolytes after they have been treated with proteins. It has also been observed^{18,19} that when fine particles of glass, quartz and other indifferent materials are

shaken with a fairly dilute solution (about 0.2%) of proteins of low pH they become positively charged and behave as if they are fully covered by the molecules of the protein used.

The concentration of BSA in the solutions used by Scatchard, Coleman and Shen¹⁰ has been of the order 1×10^{-4} mole per kg. of water. Although the BSA solutions are dilute in the usual sense yet compared to a 0.2% solution their concentration is quite high and hence they can almost completely cover the surface of the electrodes used for the measurement of H^+ ion and Cl^- ion activities. Therefore, θ in equation (1) becomes nearly equal to unity and hence $(1-\theta)H_i$ can be neglected and the equation reduces to the form :

$$(H) = \theta H_s$$

When NaCl is added to the BSA solution the Na^+ ions enter the diffuse double layer, displace some H^+ ions from there and take their place. Consequently H_s and therefore, (H) , the H^+ ion activity, of the BSA solution diminishes and so the pH rises. Since θ is nearly equal to unity therefore, equation (2) assumes the form

$$pH = p(K_s) + n \log \alpha / (1-\alpha) \quad \dots (2a)$$

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that except 3.37 the other values of $p(K_s)$ are fairly constant. The value of n is 1.02 and hence its difference from unity is within the limits of experimental error. Therefore, excluding 3.37 the average of the other values of $p(K_s)$ is 3.18 which may be considered as the proper $p(K)$ of the COOH groups between pH 2.0 and 5.0.

It may be mentioned that H_b , (that is the H^+ ions bound a mole of BSA) can be calculated from equation (2a) when the constants in it are known and the pH is measured by a glass electrode.

References

1. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 185.
2. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 359.
3. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 565.
4. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 114.
5. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 463.
6. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 709.
7. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 57.
8. O. STERN, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1924, **30**, 50.
9. J. N. MUKHERJEE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1920-21, **16**, 103.
10. G. SCATCHARD, J. S. COLEMAN and A. L. SHEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 12.
11. M. NAGASAWA and A. HOLTZER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 531.
12. M. RANDALL and L. E. YOUNG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 989.
13. D. I. HITCHCOCK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 2076.
14. R. ZSIGMONDY, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1901, **40**, 697.
15. H. FREUNDLICH, *Kapillarchemie II*, Leipzig., 1932, 449.
16. A. SILBERBERG, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **48**, 2835.
17. F. TH. HESSELINK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 65.
18. H. A. ABRAMSON, L. S. MOYER and M. H. GORIN, "Electrophoresis of Proteins", New York, 1942, p. 152 et seq.
19. D. K. CHATTORAJ and H. B. BULL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 5128.